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Assessing the Impact of Remittances on the Welfare and Upward Mobility of Nigerian Households

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the assessment of the impact of remittances on the Welfare and Upward Mobility of Nigerian Households, the largest remittance recipient in Sub-Saharan Africa. Using mixed methods surveys, interviews, and secondary data the research finds that remittances mainly support basic needs such as food, housing, and healthcare, with smaller portions directed toward education, savings, and entrepreneurship. While regression analysis shows a positive effect on welfare and mobility, the impact is constrained by factors like education, financial inclusion, household size, and rural–urban disparities. Qualitative evidence further reveals challenges such as dependency on remittances and low financial literacy. The study concludes that remittances function as a “double-edged sword”: they improve household well-being but fall short of transformational change due to structural barriers. It recommends policies to reduce transaction costs, enhance financial inclusion, and address investment barriers to shift remittances from short-term relief to drivers of sustainable development and inclusive growth.

Keywords: Remittances, Household Welfare, Social Mobility, Poverty Reduction, Financial Inclusion

INTRODUCTION

International migration and the flow of remittances have become defining features of globalisation and the development of the twenty-first century. Remittances - cross-border financial transfers sent by migrant workers to their family members within their home countries - have, within the last two decades, become one of the most critical external financial instruments to low and middle-income countries (Ratha et. al, 2020). As of 2022, global remittance inflows were estimated to reach \$794 billion, out of which \$626 billion were sent to developing economies. This inflow of funds dwarfs foreign direct investment and official development assistance in many regions of the world (World Bank, 2022). As with other external financial flows, remittances in cross-border payments and transfers emerge as one of the most stable, counter-cyclical, and directly delivered forms of household support (Giuliano & Ruiz-Arranz, 2020).

In Sub-Saharan Africa, Nigeria stands as the country that receives the most remittances and ranks among the top ten countries worldwide. According to the World Bank (2020), the country received an estimated \$ 23.8 billion in remittances, which amounts to 6% of the country's GDP in 2019. These remittances originate from the Nigerian immigrants in the United States, Canada, Europe, and the Middle East and have become crucial to the survival of numerous families. According to research, the volume of remittances received, in terms of the development aid received by the country, and in terms of household consumption and poverty alleviation, is comparable to the revenue generated from the country's oil (Olayungbo & Quadri, 2019; Abiola & Ajibola, 2022). At the micro-level, research indicates that remittances from family and friends are a crucial factor in alleviating poverty, as well as in meeting basic needs (such as food, housing, and clothing), funding education, healthcare, and small businesses (Adams & Page, 2020; Ebeke, 2012).

Apart from the welfare aspects, remittances contribute to social mobility, the process by which individuals or families move up the socio-economic class system. Improvements in recipients' opportunities and in social progress, created by remittances, can be intergenerational (Dustmann & Mestres, 2010). In the rural areas of Nigeria, where formal employment and credit are not as easily accessible (Abeke et al., 2025), remittances are the primary source of investment in human capital and productive activities (Osili, 2004).

Even with these contributions, the developmental impact of remittances on the economy remains a point of contention. Some authors contend that remittances create a culture of dependency, discourage participation in the labour market, and deepen the inequality gap between households that receive and do not receive remittances (Chami et al., 2019; Mishra, 2020). Others emphasise persistent barriers to effectiveness, including exorbitant transfer fees, fragile financial structures, low levels of financial literacy, and a dominance of informal transfer mechanisms (Magaji et al., 2025b; Ratha et al, 2020). Furthermore, while evidence on the poverty-alleviating impact of remittances is widespread, very few studies have sought to understand the remittances in the form of the tools that contribute to and foster social mobility in Nigeria.

This paradox is particularly striking in the case of Nigeria, as remittance inflows fail to address the worsening poverty and inequality. As the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2022) states, over 40% of Nigeria's population is living below the poverty line. The country also suffers high rates of unemployment and underemployment (Magaji et al., 2022). Remittances undoubtedly help alleviate short-term financial difficulties for households; however, their long-term economic effects are highly uncertain. Economically active individuals, in many cases, receive remittances with the primary purpose of consumption over investment, raising the question of whether remittances serve as a means for socioeconomic ascension or a mere survival tactic (Odozi et al., 2010; Abdu & Ayodele, 2021). Also, there are regional disparities: urban households with remittances have better long-term economic prospects due to better education and financial services than rural households.

A critical gap now emerges. Past research on remittances in Nigeria has centred on macroeconomic equilibrium, poverty alleviation, or relative to economic growth (Olayungbo & Quadri, 2019; Abiola & Ajibola, 2022). Very few have assessed the impact of remittances on household welfare and social mobility, especially from a social mobility intergenerational lens. This gap needs to be filled in order to ascertain whether or not remittances only subsidise poverty in the short run, or whether they have enduring positive effects on living standards and economic prospects.

In light of this, this study aims to explore the impact of remittances on household welfare and social mobility in Nigeria. It specifically determines the level of household welfare attained in education, healthcare, housing, and consumption; assesses the level of social mobility attained through human capital and positive net worth, and entrepreneurial investments; determines the challenges that hinder the proper utilisation of remittances; and analyses the differences in their utilisation between rural and urban relative to rural households. This study, in addressing the above objectives, contributes to the discourse on the impact of remittances in Nigeria as to whether they are primarily a tool for poverty alleviation or a means for fostering enduring, inclusive growth.

Review of Literature

There is a growing focus on remittances due to their increasing importance for the development of households and overall prosperity in developing and emerging economies. Broadly speaking, remittances refer to money or gifts sent home by migrants to their families or communities of origin (Magaji et al., 2025a). Unlike other types of financial flows, remittances are private, stable and counter-cyclical, meaning they increase in volume during periods of economic decline or crisis (World Bank, 2020). Household welfare captures the overall well-being of people and families (Ibrahim & Sule, 2023), proportionately to the ease with which they can access food, education, healthcare, housing and a means of livelihood (Musa et al., 2024). Social mobility is the phenomenon by which a person or a family can ascend the social and economic ladder, often over several generations, because of increased investments in education, healthcare, skill development and other productive resources (OECD, 2018).

In theory, several scholars have developed different frameworks to assess the role of remittances in development. The New Economics of Labour Migration (NELM) theory postulates that remittances are part of the household strategies to manage risks, overcoming blank credit and blank insurance in places where formal structures are scarce (Stark & Bloom, 1985). The scholar of the Human Capital Theory sits in a position to put forth that remittances enhance welfare by easing expenditures on education and health, thus improving productivity and upward mobility over several generations (Becker, 1993; Schultz, 2004). The Multiplier Effect Theory focuses on the broader spillover effects and argues that remittance spending increases local demand for goods and services, which, in turn, leads to job creation and economic expansion (Taylor, 1999). On the other hand, the Dependency Theory takes a contrary stance and argues that remittances encourage chronic dependence, disincentivise active labour force participation (Magaji & Musa, 2015), and stifle the entrepreneurial spirit (Chami et al., 2019). The more recent theorisations have also sought to apply the Financial Inclusion Theory, which centres on the ability of remittances to incorporate households into formal financial structures, fostering saving and investment (Aggarwal, Demirgüç-Kunt, & Martinez-Peria, 2011).

Most studies reviewing remittance effects on household welfare are positive. As Page and Adams noted, remittances reduce poverty in developing countries by nearly 11 per cent, and drastically lower the share of the population living under \$1.90 a day. In Sub-Saharan Africa, remittances have been shown to support household consumption, improve access to education, and reduce child labour (Ebeke, 2012). In particular, Olayungbo and Quadri 2019 showed that in Nigeria, remittances have a positive impact on the GDP and simultaneously lower the poverty rate, while Abiola and Ajibola 2022 showed that remittances increase aggregate household expenditure on health, education, and housing. Also, as Osili (2004) noted, households in Nigeria that receive remittances are more likely to spend money on education than those without, illustrating the importance of investment in human capital.

The link between social mobility and remittance, however, is more complicated. Dustmann and Mestres (2010) have observed that while remittances tend to improve educational opportunities, the lack of mobility in the labour force within certain countries suggests that structural unemployment is a pervasive problem. In Mexico, Taylor and Mora (2006) observed that the increase in remittance income does not lead to a significant increase in inter-generational occupational mobility. In Nigeria, as suggested in Odozi et al. (2010), though the effect of remittances on welfare is positive, their effect on asset accumulation and entrepreneurial activity is relatively small. It is generally a reflection of low levels of financial literacy and poor access to credit (Oyinloye et al., 2025). More recent evidence, as discussed in Abdu and Ayodele (2021), emphasises that the ability to convert remittances to enhance inter-generational mobility is more pronounced in urban areas than in rural areas, where remittances tend to be consumed.

Another strand of literature focuses on the issues of using remittances for development. High transaction costs are still a barrier; the cost of sending \$200 to Sub-Saharan Africa in 2020 was 8.9 per cent, much higher than the UN SDG target of 3 per cent (World Bank, 2020). Furthermore, the prevalence of informal transfer systems hinders financial inclusion (Musa et al., 2023), and the potential developmental impact of remittances is lost (Ratha et al., 2020). Chami et al. (2019) also argue that the dependence on

remittances can result in a “moral hazard” problem, which diminishes the incentives for participation in the labour market and for entrepreneurial activity. On the other hand, Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz (2020) demonstrate that in underdeveloped financial systems, remittances can provide an alternative to credit and promote investment in small-scale entrepreneurial activities.

There are still some missing pieces of the puzzle with respect to the Nigerian situation, despite the extensive documentation. Most of the available literature has tackled the macroeconomic consequences of remittances like their impact on GDP, balance of payments, and alleviation of poverty. At the same time, relatively few have empirically assessed the contribution to social mobility. The differences in the intergenerational impacts of remittances on education, health, and capital, as well as their variations in use by rural and urban households, are among the most significant gaps in the literature. This study takes on the challenge of assessing how remittances, in addition to welfare, determine long-term upward mobility and the associated opportunities in the context of Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

In Nigeria, the impact of remittances on social mobility and household welfare has not been examined in depth individually, as this study has done. This study used a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches in what can best be termed a mixed-methods research design. With respect to the quantitative approaches, the focus is on the spending behaviour, welfare, and social indicators of remittances on households. In contrast, the qualitative approaches focus more on the experiences of the remittance-receiving households, particularly their vantage points on long-term mobility and the cons of remittance assistance. The combination of the aforementioned approaches assisted in strengthening the findings, thereby enhancing the study’s validity and reliability.

The study population was made up of households in Nigeria which receive remittances from migrants. Considering the geographical and socio-economic aspects of the country, the sample was divided along rural and urban lines to examine how the use and effects of remittances differed, if at all. A multi-stage sampling technique was used. In the first stage, data were collected from purposefully selected states in each of the country’s central regions to gauge the intensity of international migration and remittance inflows, as set by the Central Bank of Nigeria. In the second stage, local government areas (LGAs) in each selected state were the focus, within which remittance-receiving households were randomly sampled. A total of 400 households took part in the survey, which was a large enough sample to support sound statistical analysis. Data was collected by administering a structured questionnaire to the head of the household or the primary decision maker. The study captured the demographic data of the respondents, the types and volumes of remittances received, the spending patterns of the households, the welfare outcomes (food security, access to health care, education, and housing), and the social mobility proxies (ownership of durable assets, business start-up, and education level of children). Complementing the quantitative survey, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 30 identified households to explore the long-term impact of remittances on opportunity, aspiration, and potential dependency. Secondary data from the World Bank, IMF, CBN and National Bureau of Statistics were also added to the study for further analysis and background.

For this report, I have split the data analysis into stages. In the first stage, it summarised the data concerning the socio-economic characteristics of households along with the reported uses of remittances using descriptive statistics like means, percentages, and frequency distributions. This showed the extent of the contribution of remittances to welfare enhancement. In the second stage, it performed multiple regressions to determine the effect of remittances on household welfare and the effect of household welfare on social mobility. To proxy household welfare, it computed a composite index that captures food security, access to healthcare, and quality of housing. At the same time, social mobility was assessed through education, business ownership, and asset possession. It calculated the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression results for the effects of the remittances, controlling for the household characteristics of the education of the household head, residence, financial services accessibility, and household size. To

check robustness, it ran model diagnostics, and for the models, it checked significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

All participants were treated with the utmost respect. They were aware of the study’s objectives and the scope of the study; participation was optional, and respondents’ privacy was protected. The primary and secondary sources of qualitative and quantitative information created a robust methodology that captured the attributes and assessed the impacts of remittance, social mobility, and welfare in Nigeria.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Utilisation of remittances by Households

Households’ use of remittances in Nigeria is illustrated in Table 1 together with the distribution of remittances by primary uses. The results show that the highest portion of remittances is spent on food and subsistence, with about 92 per cent. This is followed by healthcare (70 per cent) and education (63 per cent).

Housing (58 per cent) and investment in informal micro enterprises (45 per cent) also constitute significant uses, while the net savers or investors of remittances accounted for the minority. This was 28 per cent of the total.

Table 1: Distribution of Remittances by Major Uses among Households in Nigeria

Use of Remittances	Percentage of Households (%)
Education (school fees, books)	63.0
Healthcare (medical bills, drugs)	70.0
Food and Daily Consumption	92.0
Housing (rent, renovation, utilities)	58.0
Small Business/Entrepreneurship	45.0
Savings and Investments	28.0
Social/Community Events	22.0

Source: Field Survey (2025)

These findings underscore the significance of remittances in sustaining household consumption and basic welfare, as noted by Adams and Page (2020), as remittances primarily serve as a means of income smoothing in developing countries. The low allocation, however, set aside for savings and investment, indicates that the development spending potential of remittances is not fully appreciated. This is the situation along the lines that Chami et al. (2019) worry about, where remittances are aimed at consumption that fosters dependency. On the other hand, the evidence of investments in education and healthcare suggests that remittances serve to enhance the formation of human capital, as is the case with the theory of Human Capital (Becker, 1993), which supports the narrative for mobility over time.

Improvements in Household Welfare

Table 2 shows improvements in household welfare due to remittances. Eighty-five per cent of households indicated improvements in food security, 70 per cent reported improvements in access to healthcare, 63 per cent reported improvements in education, and there were also positive impacts on the quality of housing, as well as on clothing and household goods.

Table 2: Reported Improvements in Household Welfare from Remittances

Welfare Indicator	% of Households Reporting Improvement
Food Security	85.0
Access to Healthcare	70.0
Access to Education	63.0
Housing Quality	58.0
Clothing and Household Goods	52.0

Source: Field Survey (2025)

These findings bolster the argument for the positive effect of remittances on the standard of living. Also supports Osili (2004) regarding remittance households in Nigeria having a higher probability of investing in education. Also, Ebeke (2012) has noted the rising expenditures with health status in the African

Region and with the New Remittances: A Multi-Disciplinary Perspective Supported By Several Defendants/Proven Related Agreements’ Economics of Labour Migration (Stark & Bloom, 1985)—which argues that remittances aid households in resolving local market limitations by funding critical services. However, these results underscore the predominance of mere improvements in welfare over fundamental economic transformation, as noted by Mishra (2020), who points out that remittance-driven welfare improvements are elusive in the absence of structural transformation.

The Effect of Remittances on the Socioeconomic Promotion of Households

Table 3 assesses the effect of remittances on the socioeconomic status of households. Seventy-six per cent of respondents claim their households are better off. Sixty-one per cent of respondents claim the children’s educational achievements surpass the parents’ goals. Forty-eight per cent claim their households have better job opportunities. Forty-five per cent claim their households have the capability of starting or growing businesses. However, the number of households that claim to possess considerable wealth is 39 per cent.

Table 3: Perceived Impact of Remittances on Social Mobility

Indicator	Percentage of Households (%)
Improved educational attainment of children	61.0
Better employment opportunities	48.0
Improved standard of living	76.0
Ability to start or expand a business	45.0
Ownership of assets (land, housing, etc.)	39.0

Source: Field Survey (2025)

These studies show the strengths and weaknesses of remittances when it comes to social mobility. The data show that intergenerational progress is possible because of increased living standards, supporting the Human Capital Theory and the study of Adams and Page (2020). However, the overall impact on asset accumulation and employment opportunities is still low, which indicates that remittances are not enough to guarantee long-term intergenerational mobility and that other structural factors are necessary. This further corroborates the observation by Taylor and Mora (2006) in Mexico that while remittances increase income at the household level, they do not necessarily increase occupational mobility. In the case of Nigeria, these factors may be attributed to structural unemployment, a poorly developed credit market, and a low level of entrepreneurial activity, particularly in rural areas (Abdu & Ayodele, 2021).

Problems Affecting the Use of Remittances

The data in Table 4 shows the challenges facing the households that receive remittances. Most of them have observed high transaction costs (41 per cent), limited access to financial services (37 per cent), and low financial literacy (34 per cent). Dependence on remittances was also identified by 29 per cent of the survey participants, along with 26 per cent who emphasised the persistent use of informal transfer services.

Table 4: Challenges in the Utilisation of Remittances

Challenge	Percentage of Households (%)
High transaction costs	41.0
Limited access to financial services	37.0
Low financial literacy	34.0
Over-dependence on remittances	29.0
Use of informal transfer channels	26.0

Source: Field Survey (2025)

These findings provide insight into serious barriers that hinder the economic growth that remittances have the potential to bring. Transfer costs, as estimated by the World Bank (2020), are a significant barrier to remittances, with Sub-Saharan Africa being the most expensive region in the world for remittance transfers. The lack of financial services is a barrier for households to invest their remittances in productive activities, as Aggarwal et al. (2011) described the need to link remittances to financial services. The dependency is also referred to by Chami et al. (2019), who warned that remittances may

lessen the motivation to participate in the labour market or create new businesses. All together, these barriers affirm the need for thoughtful changes in policy that reduce costs of remittance transfer, access to formal financing, and financial education to remittance-receiving households.

Regression Analysis: Changes in Household Welfare

Remittances and household welfare are also analysed in Table 5, which illustrates the results of the regressions for the welfare of the household. In this case, the impact of remittances is positive and robust, and it is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.421$, $p < 0.01$). Also, having a head of household with a positive and statistically significant education ($\beta = 0.216$, $p < 0.05$), along with being in an urban area ($\beta = 0.194$, $p < 0.05$), positively contributes to welfare. However, an increased household size, on the whole, detracts from household welfare ($\beta = -0.138$, $p < 0.05$). The model accounts for 64 per cent of the variation in the outcomes of household welfare.

Table 5: Regression Results – Impact of Remittances on Household Welfare

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Remittances (amount received)	0.421	0.072	5.85	0.000***
Household size	-0.138	0.045	-3.07	0.002**
Education level of household head	0.216	0.063	3.43	0.001**
Urban residence (dummy)	0.194	0.057	3.40	0.001**
Constant	2.107	0.186	11.32	0.000***

$R^2 = 0.64$; Adj. $R^2 = 0.61$; F-statistic = 22.3 ($p < 0.01$)

Dependent Variable: Household Welfare Index

The evidence does show that remittances do enhance welfare, which is in alignment with the descriptive results and the existing literature (Adams & Page, 2020; Olayungbo & Quadri, 2019). The significance of education, as well as urban residence, suggests that structural and contextual factors indeed play a role in amplifying the remittance benefits. Primarily, urban households are in a better position to direct remittances to welfare-enhancing activities, as educated heads of households are likely to invest in human capital. This suggests that remittances are not the only factor that determines the impact of a household, as several other household factors and local opportunities are likely to dictate the impact as well.

Regression Analysis: Effects on Social Mobility

Table 6 depicts the results of regressions on the impacts of remittances on social mobility. As before, remittances again exert a strong positive effect ($\beta = 0.357$, $p < 0.01$), and also education of the household head ($\beta = 0.289$, $p < 0.01$), and access to mobility outcome enhancing financial services ($\beta = 0.174$, $p < 0.05$) mobility outcome enhancing financial services. Household size has a negative impact ($\beta = -0.092$, $p < 0.1$), and urban residence impacts mobility positively ($\beta = 0.145$, $p < 0.05$). The model accounts for 59 per cent of the variance in the social mobility outcome.

Table 6: Regression Results – Impact of Remittances on Social Mobility

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Remittances (amount received)	0.357	0.084	4.25	0.000***
Household size	-0.092	0.038	-2.42	0.016*
Education level of household head	0.289	0.077	3.75	0.000***
Access to financial services (dummy)	0.174	0.069	2.52	0.013*
Urban residence (dummy)	0.145	0.061	2.38	0.018*
Constant	1.963	0.209	9.39	0.000***

$R^2 = 0.59$; Adj. $R^2 = 0.56$; F-statistic = 19.6 ($p < 0.01$)

Dependent Variable: Social Mobility Index

Social Mobility Index is the dependent variable in this analysis

These findings highlight the fact that remittances enable upward mobility. However, the ultimate benefits can only be realised with education, a suitable geographical location, the inclusion of formal financial services, and other structural opportunities that sustain location mobility. The positive relationship with formal financial services is in line with Financial Inclusion Theory (Aggarwal et al, 2011), which emphasises the role of formal financial services in the process of remittance. On the other hand, the size of the household is negatively correlated with the amount of remittances received, which indicates that the sharing of remittances within larger households weakens their potential benefits on development. All in all, the findings suggest that remittances, in the absence of deeper structural and institutional frameworks, can serve as a basis for upward mobility.

Findings Discussion

In reverse economics, the findings show the importance of remittances in Nigeria. First, they provide welfare benefits through food, education, health, and even investment in small businesses. However, the potential of remittance alone in promoting sustained social mobility is significantly constrained by structural barriers, including financial exclusion, high transaction costs, and the limited social mobility between rural and urban dwellers. As Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz (2020) argue, these findings support the notion that remittances serve as a credit substitute in peripheral and underdeveloped financial markets. They also support the well-worn concerns of Chami et al. (2019) regarding inequality and dependency. To be a change agent, remittances require deliberate policy frameworks aimed at reducing transactional costs, improving financial accessibility, and fostering investment in financially constrained regions.

Conclusion and Policy Considerations

This study explored how remittances influence household welfare and social mobility in Nigeria. The evidence strongly supports the notion that remittances significantly alleviate some common challenges faced by families. The evidence strongly supports the notion that remittances significantly alleviate some common challenges faced by families. This also fosters economic mobility through investments in human capital and small entrepreneurship. Such outcomes further accentuate the stabilising and poverty alleviation roles remittances play in the absence of formal employment and social protection systems.

Despite the advantages brought by remittances, the study claims that the advantages are only in part, if at all, distributionally transformative. In the short run, the cash does cushion deprivation. However, the dominant part of the inflow being used on consumption does not guarantee improvement in sustainable livelihood or progress as a society intergenerationally. Also, high transaction costs, the absence of formal financial services, financial illiteracy, financial system gaps, and spatial inequalities are a bottleneck to the transformative potential of remittances. Compared to the rural population, urban households are in a better position to invest the remittances, thereby reaping the long-term benefits. The rural and urban disparity in education and financial services widens the gap in investments in welfare, mobility, and education. Remittances subsidise desert life. They are a boosted financial system. They are a double-edged sword. They do supportive systems, and do not. Socio-economic inequalities do not get bridged. Socio-economic divides increase. Policies designed to capture the full value potential of remittances need to respond to both structural and behavioural barriers. Households retain more remittances sent by migrants when sending the money for migration is cheaper due to greater competition. Savings, credit, and productive investment opportunities emerge when remittances sent by migrants are integrated with financial systems such as mobile money, microfinance, and banking. Households also need financial education on how to optimise the allocation of strategic remittances by shifting expenditure focus from consumption to education, investment, and asset acquisition.

Building productive investments is also critical, such as diaspora bonds and cooperative housing reforms. These investments link remittance flows to infrastructure, small businesses, and capital formation. Equity is essential as rural households are more vulnerable to poverty and social exclusion. These households require focused education, healthcare, and financial exclusion moderation for the development region

across which remittances are sent and utilised. Also important is the need to break the over-reliance on remittance receipts. Policies should focus on job creation, entrepreneurship, and skills enhancement for growth.

To sum up, the remittances in Nigeria are both a lifeline and an opportunity. Improving welfare and contributing to mobility are positive attributes that enhance social structure, but the lasting impact still needs the remittance to be woven into national and household plans. With a policy that supports productive use, lower costs, and boosts financial inclusion, remittances can move from a tool of survival to a vibrant, workable stream of upward social mobility, economic growth and inclusion.

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